

Implementation Of Value And Moral Philosophy In Multicultural Education In School

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Abstract-The purpose of this study was to describe the philosophical education of moral values in terms of three aspects, namely ontology, epistemology, and axiology. The ontology aspects of value and moral philosophy are the rules, the code of conduct, the desire to do something good, to the behavior carried out by someone. To examine the values and moral philosophy, the observation method can be used because it can produce a more comprehensive study based on direct observation of conditions that occur in community life. Value and moral philosophy in terms of axiology aspect function to know and understand the meaning of values and rules in the community so that they can show good behavior in creating order in life. Value and moral philosophy are important to learn because they can develop dimensions of morality, namely moral knowing, moral feeling, and moral acting

Keywords : Value And Moral Philosophy; Multicultural Education; School

Introduction

One universal phenomenon discussed in the thinking of an academic group and the general public is morality. Morality is a characteristic that distinguishes humans from animals. Morality refers to the awareness that humans have on good and bad things, may or may not, as well as inappropriate or inappropriate. All of them are related to natural requirements and moral requirements. Natural requirements occur automatically according to natural law, while moral requirements are laws that require humans to do or not do something.

Today, there are various problems with national morality. The concern experienced by most people today is the existence of a prolonged moral decadence that results in a decline in human dignity. The quality of humanity is always related to the values of morality in real life, both in individual and social life, as well as in the form of relationships with nature and The Creator. Therefore, the issue of values and morals is a problem that will never be finished to be discussed.

Under these conditions, philosophical thinking is needed or radical and deep thinking to the root of the problem. Philosophy is systematic thinking through contemplation. However, philosophical contemplation is different from daydreaming. Kattsoff (2004) stated that philosophical contemplation is an attempt to construct a rational and adequate knowledge system to understand the world as a place to live and to understand oneself.

Value and moral philosophy is a field of study that must be performed by someone to be said to be good and not violate the prevailing norms in the community, the way a person does it, as

well as the reasons for that person doing good. In this case, value and moral philosophy aim to find evidence with rational reasons for goodness and truth.

Therefore, value and moral philosophy can be viewed from various aspects, both philosophical, sociological, theological, and anthropological aspects. Value and moral philosophy in philosophical perspectives examine what, why, and how an action is said to be good or bad and in accordance or not in accordance with the values that develop in society. In the view of sociology, value and moral philosophy include social community philosophy and political philosophy which talks about the position, role, and function of human beings in the structure of society and political dynamics that occur so that they can carry out their tasks properly and correctly.

Value and moral philosophy in theological perspective are all the good things that come from the teachings of God. In this case, good values related to morality are manifestations of the teachings of God. While in the anthropology review, value and moral philosophy include a discussion of what is human? How are human origins? How are human relations to nature, lust, and dogma?

In this study, the authors described values and moral philosophy based on the perspective of philosophy, sociology, and anthropology as the basis in the process of thinking based on value and moral philosophy because values and morals do not only cover human beings as individuals but position humans as creatures of God that must carry out the obligation, as a social creature that must establish relationships with other humans, as well as creatures that have a culture.

Method

This qualitative study in philosophy was carried out to understand social phenomena based on the view of actors. The descriptive qualitative study is basically rooted in the natural setting as a whole by relying on humans as an instrument of study. The descriptive method was used to explain and direct the subjects of study to find theories descriptively, to prioritize the process rather than the results, to discuss the study with a focus on the study design agreed by the researchers with the objects and subjects of study. This study can be used to examine an object, either in the form of human cultural values, philosophical thinking, ethical values, the value of artworks, a group of people, events, or other cultural objects.

Data were collected by (a) recording the entire essence of the data on the data card using sentences compiled by the researchers themselves. (b) quotation data recording or recording data from data sources directly and precisely. (c) synoptic recording of data or recording data from data sources by making an overview or summary. In addition, the data was organized by providing codes for each data sub-system, according to their respective classifications. Furthermore, the organization and processing of data were carried out by using: (1) Data reduction, where qualitative data from the literature is verbal data, in a long and wide description that was selected and reduced without changing the essence of its meaning, and determined its meaning according to the characteristics of the object of study. (2) The classification of the data was carried out after being reduced and then the data classification was carried out. The classification was performed by grouping based on the object of study, axiology, epistemology in philosophy in Lampung culture, ontology, and others. (3) Displaying data or organizing data in accordance with the study map. Data were displayed by creating networks or schematization related to the context.

Results and Discussion

1. Value and moral philosophy in philosophical perspective

Before discussing the value and moral philosophy in philosophical perspectives, it is better to understand values and morals. Value as a concept is widely known in the science of philosophy about the way a person views things both on goods and humans.

Explicitly, value refers to the things performed by humans, whether it is good or bad, good and bad, high and low, and so forth. However, "value" as developed in community life is often judged as something that has good value, something that is valuable, quality, and useful to humans. Value is very closely related to morals, ethics, and aesthetics which are all used as a reference by humans to behave in everyday life. Something is considered to have value if something is useful for human life.

Today, people throughout the world are aware of the importance of values in all aspects of life, including the dangers to human life, if it is not based on good value or value-free. Value as a reference in human life experiences development from time to time that follows the dynamics that have developed in the community since the days of human ancestors. This is in line with a statement by Kurt Baier (Sauri, 2007) that value is a behavioral tendency that starts from psychological symptoms such as desires, motives, attitudes, needs, and beliefs that are individually owned to the unique behavior. This shows that the value is developed and carried out by individuals or humans for the needs and beliefs that are implemented in the form of good behavior.

The moral is derived from the Latin "mores" which means custom. In the Indonesian language, moral means inner discipline which guides mental behavior in life. According to Kaelan (2001), morals are teachings, discourses, standards, a collection of rules both oral and written on how to live and act to be a good human being. Kohlberg (Reimer, 1995) defined that morality is not a collection of certain rules, norms, or behaviors but is a perspective.

Value and moral philosophy exist to answer various questions about a certain attitude or behavior. These attitudes include good or bad and are proper or improper where the rules and codes of conduct that develop in the community are the starting point. Philosophically, value and moral philosophy can be viewed from three aspects, namely ontology, epistemology, and axiology.

a. Value and moral philosophy based on ontology

Ontology is the study of reality, both concrete and abstract. Ontology is a science or pillars of science that question the science of what objects are studied by science, the form of the object, the relationship between objects and human comprehension that produce knowledge.

The object of values and morals is a rule, code of conduct, and the desire of someone to do something good, to the behavior carried out by someone. Kluckhon (Mulyana, 2004) defined value as a conception of what is desired, which influences the choice of means, intermediate goals, and ultimate goals of action. In this case, value and moral philosophy examine the motive of someone to do something, including the way performed until the results to be obtained.

In relation to the form of value and moral philosophy, Notonegoro (Budiyono, 2009) stated that value is not only attached to something that has a form but can be attached to something abstract that can only be felt by humans. Notonegoro divided three main values, viz:

- 1) Material value shows something useful for human physical elements.
- 2) Vital value shows something useful for humans to be able to carry out activities in life.
- 3) Religious value shows something useful for human spirituality. Religious value is divided into:
 - a) the value of truth or fact that originates in human reason (ratio)
 - b) the beauty value that originates in human aesthetics
 - c) the religious value that originates in human trust accompanied by appreciation through reason and conscience.

From the explanation above, the form of value and moral is not only attached to something concrete but more meaningful to something abstract that cannot be seen but can be felt. For example, whether someone is doing something meaningful or not, whether someone is doing good or bad that is certainly decided based on feelings attached to humans on the suitability between the behavior carried out with values that are recognized as universal truth.

b. Value and moral philosophy based on epistemology

Epistemology or theory of knowledge is a branch of philosophy that deals with the nature and scope of knowledge, presuppositions, and basics, as well as accountability for statements about the knowledge, possessed. Therefore, in principle, epistemology discusses the source of knowledge, the origin of knowledge, boundaries, characteristics, methods, and expertise of knowledge. Therefore, the systematic writing of epistemology is the origin of knowledge, theories about truth, scientific methods, and schools of thought.

To study the value and moral philosophy, the observation method can be used. The observation method is used because it is to study further the values that develop in the community.

Observation focuses on an object by using all the senses. Arikunto (1998) stated that "observation is carried out by observers using both observation instruments and without observation instruments". Observation allows researchers to feel what is felt and lived by the subject so that it allows researchers to become a source of data.

Data from observations are expected to be more factual about the situation and conditions of research activities in the field. According to Patton (1980), the benefits of observational data are as follows:

- 1) By being in the field, researchers better understand the context of data in the whole situation, so researchers can obtain a holistic view.
- 2) Direct experience allows researchers to use an inductive approach so that it cannot be influenced by previous concepts or views. The inductive approach opens the possibility of discovery.
- 3) Researchers can see things that are lacking or not observed by others, especially people who are in the environment, because it has been considered "ordinary" and therefore will not be revealed in the interview.
- 4) Researchers can find things outside of public perception so that a more comprehensive description can be obtained.

Through this method, researchers can think deeply about the values and morality that develop in a society, because values and morality are things that are created and believed by a group of people in their community. Therefore, researchers can find out what things are judged good and what things are judged bad based on the basis and rationality that develops in society.

The method of scientific thinking is a way to apply logical principles to the discovery, validation, and explanation of truth. Therefore, the scientific method is a systematic method used by scientists to solve problems. The things that scientists must do on the object of value and moral philosophy are as follows:

- 1) Understanding of symbols, words or codes and various terms used by the community as objects of empirical research.
- 2) Understanding of the theories of value and morals that view an action can be said to be good or bad.
- 3) An understanding of the rules or code of conduct that develops and is recognized as appropriate in a society.
- 4) The ability to think in seeing trends in changing patterns of community behavior for certain causes.

c. Value and moral philosophy based on axiology

Axiology is a branch of philosophy that discusses value and meaning as something valuable, quality, meaningful, and purposeful for the lives of humans, individuals, and groups. According to Kattsoff (2004), axiology is a science that investigates the nature of values. Therefore, when discussing nature it is related to the purpose or benefit to be gained from something.

Value and moral philosophy, when viewed from the aspect of axiology, has the purpose of knowing and understanding the significance of values and rules that apply in the community so that they show good behavior in creating order in life. Value and moral philosophy are important to learn because they can develop what is called by Lickona (2004) as the dimension of morality which includes:

- 1) moral knowing includes moral awareness, moral insight, perspective, moral reasoning, decision making, and self-understanding.
- 2) moral feeling includes conscience, self-confidence, empathy, love, kindness, self-control, and self-esteem.
- 3) moral acting includes competence, willingness, and habits.

By examining the values and moral philosophy, it is hoped that a social order will be formed that respects and upholds the values of universal goodness, has a moral feeling and can ultimately carry out moral actions in daily life. Moral habits support the creation of an orderly, safe, and prosperous life because everything performed in accordance with things that are recognized together as a good and meaningful act.

2. Value and moral philosophy in sociological perspective

Sociology is known as a study of society, patterns of interaction, social contracts and human relations with other humans. Emile Durkheim (Sunarto, 2004) stated that sociology is a science that studies social facts or ways of acting, thinking, and feeling that are outside the individual and have the power to force control.

Based on a statement by Durkheim, sociology covers the process of thinking and acting. This is related to morality or knowledge on civilized human character. Moral means good and bad teachings. Value and morals are the result of community agreements on things that should be performed and should not be performed or morals on good and bad things.

Moral comes from the Latin word "mores" which means "rules of decency". Therefore, literally, morals are rules of decency, which include all norms of good behavior and conduct. In this context, good behavior does not interfere with the rights of others. Max Weber (Sunarto, 2004) stated that sociology is a study of social action taken by considering the behavior of others and oriented to the behavior of others.

In a community, there are various rules to be carried out in daily life, including in regulating how humans relate to other humans. Therefore there is the term "politeness". Politeness is a good value to regulate someone to behave pleasantly for others.

Politeness is a rule of life that arises because of a desire to please others, outsiders, daily relationships, community, governance and others. Basically, politeness is appropriateness, appropriateness, habits, concerns that apply in association (community, government, nation and state). Politeness is emphasized on the outward attitude of each subject for the sake of community life in association. Sanctions for violations of politeness are reproach in the midst of environmental society, for example being ostracized in association.

Based on the above explanation, value and moral philosophy are viewed from a sociological perspective on the good things that must be performed in a social interaction. The quality of a behavior displayed depends on the agreement made by the community. A value and moral philosophy expert must be able to examine the structure and behavior that develops in society radically, deeply, systematically and comprehensively so that they are not trapped in superficial understanding and easy to make judgment in analyzing a situation.

The value and moral philosophy in sociological perspective also supports the creation of civil society that makes civilization values as the basis for carrying out community, nation, and state life. According to Sauri (2012), the characteristics of civil society are as follows:

- a. Godhead
- b. Peace
- c. Mutual cooperation
- d. Tolerant
- e. Balance between rights and social obligations
- f. High civilization, and
- g. Good morals

Tilaar & Mukhlis (1999) stated that there are 4 main characteristics of civil society, namely:

- a. Volunteering shows that civil society membership is free which voluntarily forms a shared life and has a very large shared commitment to realizing shared ideals. According to Tilaar, civil society is formed not based on coercion of a country but formed because there is a common view of the importance of living in groups.
- b. Self-sufficiency shows that civil society upholds independence in life. Every community member has high self-esteem and is always responsible for self and other community members.
- c. High independence of the country shows that civil society is very confident and upholds the principle of popular sovereignty. As an independent society, civil society does not depend on the orders of others, including the country.
- d. The linkage to mutually agreed legal values shows that civil society is very committed to the rules and norms that bind freedom which is the result of mutual agreement between communities (the result of consensus)

In the development of Indonesian civil society, there are several distinctive characteristics (Sauri, 2012), namely:

- a. The diversity of Indonesian culture as the basis for the development of Indonesian national identity and national culture.
- b. The importance of mutual understanding between members of the community.
- c. Has a high tolerance, because Indonesian people are formed not through a process of indoctrination but knowledge of diversity and appreciation of diversity as an important element in national development.
- d. To implement these unique values, a life together with legal certainty is needed.

3. Value and moral philosophy in anthropological perspective

Anthropology is a study of humanity. Etymologically, anthropology comes from the words "Anthropos" which means humans and "logos" which means science. Anthropology views humans as complex in terms of their physical, emotional, social, and cultural aspects. Anthropology is often referred to as the science of humans and their culture.

There are at least five problems examined in anthropology (Koentjaraningrat, 1985), namely:

- a. The history of the origin and development of humans (or its evolution) biologically;
- b. The history of the occurrence of various human colors is seen based on body characteristics;
- c. The history of the origin, development, and distribution of languages spoken by humans throughout the world;
- d. Development, distribution, and occurrence of various kinds of human culture throughout the world;
- e. The principles of ethnic culture that are spread throughout the world today.

Based on the scope of anthropology above, it can be said that values and moral philosophy in anthropological perspective examines the origin of humans, language development which becomes a communication tool and the spread of values that develop in the community promotes tolerance and respects differences about human physical characteristics and respects differences community culture which in the context of Indonesia as a multicultural country is very much needed respect and appreciation for cultural diversity.

Today, the problem that occurs in Indonesia is the low appreciation of the community for Indonesian culture. The weakening of community appreciation for Indonesian native culture occurs as a result of the absence of filters on various kinds of cultures from outside, both from dressing, socializing, arts, and so forth.

Indonesian society is currently struck by boy bands and girl bands which many of the shows do not reflect Indonesian culture, both in terms of dressings and in terms of the content delivered. Strangely, Indonesian young people are very proud when they can dress like a boy band and girl band personnel.

According to the author, this is a problem that must be immediately sought for a solution, because if left unchecked, the original Indonesian culture will gradually disappear. One example of Indonesian culture which is internationally famous is wayang golek. On the one hand, wayang golek as one of the Indonesian cultures is recognized by UNESCO as an international cultural heritage, therefore it is proper for the Indonesian nation as the home country of the Wayang Golek to be more proud. However, in real terms, the Wayang Golek performance tradition is rarely held in Indonesia. In fact, Wayang Golek is not only an entertainment tool, but is full of values and morals that are in accordance with the personality of the Indonesian nation and always teaches all good behavior that must be carried out in social life. The Wayang Golek show displays good values and bad values based on the law of cause and effect, which gives the viewer an idea of what will be experienced when doing good and bad.

One of the moral messages conveyed in Wayang Golek is the term "manunggaling kawula gusti". The term "manunggaling kawula gusti" is one of the terms in wayang which has spiritual values. In wayang golek, human beings must be able to unite with the creator.

If someone wants to unite with God, then one must carry out certain conditions, which are to distance themselves and renounce worldly desires, besides that, humans must have noble mind

and patience, trust, sincerity, willingness, compassion and always remember the end of all events which in Sufism is known as ma'rifat (Soeparno, 2007).

Another value conveyed through the wayang golek culture is a leadership culture known as "Hastha Brata". In "Hastha Brata" there are eight leadership values (Soeparno & Soesilo, 2007), namely :

- a. Mehambeg mring kisma (earth), which means a leader must be faithful to provide the necessities of life to anyone, patient (earth as a source of life)
- b. *Mehambeg mring tirta* (water), which means a leader must always go down (people) to see and provide comfort and not lower and higher than anyone because the water is flat.
- c. Mehambeg mring semirana (wind), which means a leader must be able to interact with anyone indiscriminately and without favoritism.
- d. Mehambeg mring candra (moon), which means a leader must illuminate whoever is in the dark so that the leader can provide prosperity, beauty, and hope.
- e. Mehambeg mring surya (sun), which means a leader must give instructions as a source of life power.
- f. Mehambeg mring samudera (ocean), which means a leader must give unlimited love and freedom because the vast ocean is endless.
- g. Mehambeg mring wukir (mountain), which means a leader must be strong to protect the people.
- h. Mehambeg mring dahana (fire), a leader must be able to give warmth (able to eradicate crime and give pleasure)

Values in the culture of leadership as stated above are difficult to find in the current life of the nation and state. Only a few leaders in government, from high level to low level, can provide role models and figures as leaders, most leaders only think about personal and group interests and put aside the interests of the people that should be fought for.

Koentjaraningrat (1992), one of the foremost anthropologists in Indonesia stated that the cultural value system consists of conceptions that live in most societies on things that are valuable in life. According to Bull (1969), the development of values that a person goes through at least occurs in four stages, namely the anatomical stage, the heteronomical stage, the socionomical stage, and the autonomical stage, are as follows:

- a. Anatomical stage is a ready to be developed new value stage.
- b. Heteronomical stage is the stage of value development through rules and discipline.
- c. Socionomical stage is the stage of value development among peers and the community.
- d. Autonomical stage is the stage of developing values to fill and control conscience and free will without pressure.

After studying one of Indonesian culture (wayang golek), it can be concluded that the value and moral philosophy in terms of anthropology aspects examines the contents of moral values in a culture. Culture is the result of human creativity, taste, and initiative on the appropriateness and identity of a nation.

4. Implementation in multicultural education in school

Basically, every region with various characteristics of cultural customs teaches the community to always act well and uphold unity. However, the differences actually become a time bomb that is ready to explode at any time. For example, the customs of the Papuan people who use koteka every day are certainly different from the custom of Pasundan which is always neat. For Papuans, it might be a habit and not a distortion, but it is different from the view of the Pasundan people who actually consider it as an impropriety.

Without intending to compare customs in various regions, the author only wants to say that conflicts that are based on cultural differences do not need to occur if every element of society is aware of these differences. The difference is not something that should be debated but considers as a wealth that has a high value.

Multiculturalism is an understanding that considers cultural differences as a national treasure. Multiculturalism actually does not only occur in Indonesia, even in various countries in

the world such as America, Malaysia, and Singapore. Related to these differences, efforts must be made so that the differences do not become separators of the life of the nation and state.

The educational institution is one of the media that has a strategic position in efforts to prevent the occurrence of various conflicts of cultural background. These efforts can be performed with multicultural education through cultural laboratories. Through multicultural education, it is hoped that each community can recognize, understand, appreciate, and communicate with one another. Ainul Yaqin (2005: 5) stated that multicultural education offers an alternative through the application of educational strategies and concepts based on the use of diversity in society, especially those that exist in students such as ethnic diversity, culture, language, religion, social status, gender, ability, age, and race.

The most important thing in multicultural education is the increasing awareness of students to always be humanist, pluralist, and democratic. It is expected that students will be equipped with a variety of knowledge and understanding of cultural diversity in Indonesia so that they can apply when they graduate so that they can live in harmony and peace with communities from different cultural backgrounds. Therefore, awareness of the position as part of a diverse Indonesian nation is needed to maintain unity and integrity.

In addition to implementing a multicultural education school, one of the efforts to overcome cultural conflicts in the community is by conducting multicultural dialogue that presents several cultural figures from different regions. Hamid (2009) stated that multicultural dialogue is a method as well as a solution that is very relevant to the condition of a country with multiple cultures, ethnicities, and religions. Through dialogue, every community can understand correctly about the differences that exist in Indonesia, because multiculturalism offers a cultural perspective in understanding differences.

Conclusion

Value and moral philosophy as a multidisciplinary branch of science can be used as a tool to overcome various problems that occur in the community, in this case, moral philosophy is not only science for science but science for application. Value and moral philosophy examine the good things that must be performed in social interaction. The quality of behavior displayed depends on the agreement made by the community concerned. To examine, value and moral philosophy expert must be able to examine the structure and behavior that develops in the community radically, deeply, systematically and comprehensively so that it is not trapped in a superficial understanding and easy to make a judgment in analyzing a situation.

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